

PUNTO CRÍTICO

AUGUST - SEPTEMBER 2022
ISSUE 3

Me
CCS
MEXICAN
CARBON CAPTURE
AND
STORAGE PLATFORM

PUNTO CRÍTICO

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CDMX, México.
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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.6969255

Editor's note

The construction of scenarios can help us generate ideas, mechanisms and capacities to face the unknown and uncertainties of the future. The scenario approach has had varied applications: some companies have used it to avoid financial crises, it has been used to develop educational strategies at the national level or to glimpse the economic course that a country could follow after the election of a president, for example. The study of socio-environmental problems has found in the construction of scenarios an important way to understand what actions we must promote or make today to face the climate crisis or to achieve appropriate management of natural resources.

In this issue, you will find a note that deals with the future of CCUS written by Dr. Sallie Greenberg from the University of Illinois, as well as a reflection on the types of scenarios that could exist depending on the decisions we make today regarding energy. In the *CO₂NVERSING (CO₂NVERSANDO)* section, we include an interview with Carlos Muñoz Piña, Ph.D. in Economics of Natural Resources from the University of California at Berkeley, in which we address the possibility and implications of growth and decrease from an environmental economics perspective. In the *Yes, yes it is (Sí, sí es)* section, we have designed some scenarios that have emerged from exploring ideas derived from the current management of carbon emissions. Without a doubt, art is an important repository of futures and scenarios. For this reason, we also add a note that delves into some science fiction scenarios that have been explored in anime movies and series, specifically from the cyberpunk and solarpunk genres. We hope that this number is to your liking. Thanks for reading us!

THE PUNK OF THE FUTURE

By Adrián Fernández

Science fiction has explored imaginary situations, but at the same time plausible, that allow us to conjecture and investigate how different potential futures could be. The construction of these scenarios has been the subject of an extensive and varied artistic search through literature, cinematography, animation or theater, for instance. During the 1940s and 1950s (the golden age of science fiction), robotics and time travel were recurrent pro-tech themes, while the New Wave of the 1960s and 1970s criticized the relevance of the technological role as the only problem solver and addressed issues that had been left aside, such as discrimination, sexual freedom or environmental movements in future scenarios. Later, in the 1980s, a very particular type of science fiction emerged, cyberpunk, characterized by urban and dystopian futures in which technology plays a leading role in population control. More recently, in the context of socio-environmental conflicts, subgenres have been developed, such as *cli-fi* (climate fiction), which explores climate change scenarios, or solarpunk, which has been nourished by the concepts of sustainability to literally propose a future brighter with the use and applications of solar energy and other renewable sources, but also one philosophically and existentially more appropriate to counter social inequities. In this text, I will only focus on science fiction anime –and, true to its most orthodox definition, Japanese animation– that explores some cyberpunk and solarpunk scenarios. Of course, hundreds of other literary works, movies, animations and video games with alternative scenarios are undoubtedly worth exploring.

CYBERPUNK

Bruce Bethé invented the term *cyberpunk* to describe the juxtaposition of a world with advanced technology (represented by cybernetics) and a punk attitude, an attitude of resistance and struggle against oppression. In this scenario, the fight is directed towards mega-corporations or institutions that promote the use of technology to keep people under strict control, supervision and monitoring. It, in turn, generates profound damage to the social fabric, which reverberates in a significantly deteriorated quality of life in a climate of violence and drug use. The gloomy and gray scenarios of *cyberpunk*, where nature is usually very deteriorated or simply devastated, arose from the bias and skepticism of the 1980s regarding computational advances and paranoia about the possible replacement of humans by machines, which would become tools of control and oppression. For this reason, one of the most recurrent narratives in *cyberpunk* is a hacker-hero who, in a kind of futuristic aikido, uses the technological strength of large corporations to harm them.

Two common themes in *cyberpunk* are 1) the presence of *artificially intelligent* machines and humans who have replaced organic parts of their bodies or added parts that did not previously exist to achieve a human-machine interface: a cyborg; and 2) the existence of computational *cyberspace* (which we could currently consider as interconnected and extended digital technology: the cloud, social networks, etc.) in which

there is a global network of information exchange that is monopolized and monitored at all times. The strict control and the loss of meaning for the future trigger a mixture of corruption and fragmentation of the individual, which even reaches the sacrifice of human integrity for exaltation of technology: a cyborg is the epitome of the dissolution of borders human-machine. This idea is real and credible, as evidenced by people who have joined current transhumanist currents and call themselves cyborgs, such as Neil Harbisson, who has a bone-integrated antenna that allows skull-to-skull multimedia transmission.

Several anime series and movies have dealt with this genre: *Appleseed*, for example, explores the consequences of a hypothetical Third World War in a context where cyborgs are present. *Paprika* explores how technology affects us and changes our perception of dreams and reality, and *Psycho-Pass* addresses crime prediction using technology. *Battle Angel Alita* and *Ghost in the Shell* are among the most representative works. Both explore the limits between the organic and the technological, with cyborg female figures as protagonists. One of the iconic *cyberpunk* anime works is Katsuhiro Otomo's *Akira*, set in Neo-Tokyo, a deeply dystopian city described through traditional *cyberpunk* aesthetics: dark colors, gloomy atmospheres, and red, blue, and purple neon lights.

SOLARPUNK

In contrast, *solarpunk* explores scenarios of a sustainable civilization in which technology and nature coexist. In the *solarpunk* narrative, the heroes or heroines seek alternatives to avoid environmental catastrophes by cultivating and nurturing a future in which energy from renewable sources is particularly relevant. In this genre, the punk suffix is associated with the perennial actions and struggles to guide the "sustainability" idea: a resistance to excessive consumption economies, openness to diversity of thinking and acting, and the reinforcement of the creative struggle against social inequities. This genre explores decentralized social movements, self-organization strategies, the strengthening of communities and their productive activities, the implementation of creativity in decision-making, and the presence of female protagonists. In the *solarpunk* scenarios, an advanced technology stands out for its application in the recycling of materials or in the consolidation of online communities that constitute co-creation spaces, for example.

In terms of aesthetics, solarpunk moves away from the dystopian: it constantly uses green tones that allow us to evoke photosynthetic processes and yellow and brown tones associated with the earth. In addition, the architecture and design of buildings are based on taking advantage of existing infrastructure and materials. The emphasis of these settings, therefore, is on the subjects and not on the objects. In 2014, Adam Flynn wrote a solarpunk manifesto whose main ideas are diversity, inclusion, beauty, and promoting spaces for the coexistence between science and spirituality. Flynn emphasizes that these kinds of scenarios can definitely exist.

A very brief example of the aesthetics of solarpunk is the commercial "Eat today, feed tomorrow" of the dairy company *Chobani*, developed by the London animation

studio *The Line* (I share here the [link](#) that includes an act of resistance, as someone saw fit to remove the brand from dairy products). From Studio Ghibli, some works by director Hayao Miyazaki deal with the human-nature relationship. In particular, *Castle in the Sky* presents in some scenes a comparison of the movements of urban agriculture and the cooperation between robots and humans; *Nausicaä of the Valley of the Wind* shows a polluted planet that is considered hostile, especially for being misunderstood. The protagonist, Nausicaä, comes from a community that uses wind power and water vapor as energy sources. Her role as a human-nature link or bridge is essential for the development of the plot.

CLIMATIC SCENARIOS

Of course, there are not only scenarios in science fiction. The scientific community that has dedicated itself to studying the climate system, which is a complex system that arises from the interaction of the atmosphere, the hydrosphere, the cryosphere, the biosphere and the lithosphere, has proposed climate scenarios to understand our reality better looking to the future. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) have been created to describe and assess the social and physicochemical dimensions associated with greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, their socio-ecological effects, and the exploration of potential mitigation and adaptation to climate change. You can delve into SSPs on this [site](#). The SSPs are five distinct and plausible scenarios that are used to plan strategies nowadays in order to face the uncertainties of the future. Each one includes a narrative component and a large number of quantitative variables that serve to feed the complex models that generate them:

SSP1 - Sustainability: proposes a future with low population growth and high economic development, high levels of education, governance, a globalized society, international cooperation, technological development and environmental awareness. Under these assumptions, this scenario represents low levels of climate change mitigation and adaptation challenges.

SSP2: This is an intermediate stage between SSP1 and SSP3.

SP3 - Fragmentation: in the world, there is high population growth and low economic development, lower levels of education, regionalized societies and little environmental awareness. It represents a high level of challenges for climate adaptation and mitigation.

SSP4 - Inequality: technology advances in developed countries, but not the entire population manages to benefit from it, representing a high adaptation level.

SSP5 - Fossil fuels: globally, there is still a very high dependence on fossil fuels and low population growth; it considers high economic growth and high human development, which is why it represents a high level of challenge for mitigation.

In my opinion, and perhaps it could be considered that I am pushing the luck a bit, SSP1 can be achieved if we consider a solarpunk philosophy, where self-organization, community life, co-creation, the use of renewable sources of energy, the conscious use of high-tech when necessary and low-tech when not, the rethinking of the idea of consumption and a design philosophy oriented towards reuse and recycling are encouraged. In contrast, scenarios similar to those posed by cyberpunk do not sound so far-fetched for the narratives of fragmentation, inequality and development based on fossil fuels (SSP3, SSP4 and SSP5, respectively), which hyperconsumer societies with little environmental awareness could trigger.

It's true that far fewer examples of solarpunk than cyberpunk usually come to mind, and there is far more skepticism and incredulity surrounding a scenario like SSP1. Given this, and to finish, I can only quote Ursula Le Guin, one of the greatest science fiction writers: "We live in capitalism. This power seems inescapable. So was the divine right of kings as well. Any human power can be resisted and changed by human beings. Resistance and change often begin with art, and very often in our art, the art of words."

The possible futures of CCUS and the energy sector

By Sallie Greenberg

Reality is becoming more uncertain and complex. We are constantly in a state of change and the current situations seem to be from some science fiction world. Imagination and creativity have been determinants in human history. Today, we urgently need to evolve beyond the current reality. One of the challenges is that we, as a society, are often separated by beliefs. However, to evolve toward new realities, we need to work together to face complex challenges and solve big problems to create the best future for all, even if we disagree on how it will look like. We require integrative thinking to see beyond our current ways of knowing and solving problems. We have to get comfortable being uncomfortable and motivate ourselves to have hard conversations with people that we do not necessarily agree with. We need to understand our differences and identify our common points.

Despite how daunting all this can be, the future we are heading for is more sustainable. We have not always done the best we can in the industry or the environment, but humans have an enormous capacity to learn and adapt. This is something that sustainability requires from us.

The recently updated Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change believes that there are options available now in every sector to reduce our emissions and other environmental impacts. Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCUS) is part of the portfolio for building a sustainable future: one piece of the puzzle. CCUS is a set of technologies focused on the carbon dioxide capture, transportation, usage, and storage categories. We have developed many types of usage for CO₂: building materials, solvents for cleaning, storing food, enhanced fuel recovery, and increased crop production, among others. There are many different kinds of capture: direct air capture, capture from industrial processes and power plants, using membranes or sorbents. We have various alternatives for CO₂ transportation: ship, pipeline, and/or truck. Moreover, there are many options and locations for CO₂ storage: saline reservoirs, mature oil fields, basalts, onshore and offshore.

CCUS in any of its applications (DACCS, BECCS, blue hydrogen, etc.) requires a safe space for permanent storage of carbon dioxide. Geological storage requires proper management of subsurface resources to ensure that we are storing CO₂ in the best rocks and locations with the highest efficiency. Another critical factor is the development or repurposing of infrastructure in a sustainable and flexible way. And also, the will to use CCUS as part of our mitigation strategies is essential. There are extensive possibilities, and we cannot afford to leave off the largest and most immediate technologies that allow us to reach our sustainability goals.

In the coming years, CCUS technology will continue to be implemented in places such as the United States and Canada (onshore), Australia and the North Sea (offshore), the Netherlands, Japan, and many other places due to the potential to store large volumes of CO₂ immediately. CCUS is being demonstrated primarily in highly industrialized countries as early adopters of this technology. By contrast, in regions that are still developing and improving their economies – Latin America, Asia, and Africa – it may be less likely to see the right conditions for its adoption, due to competition for economic resources and other priorities. Over the 20+ years of being involved with CO₂ storage, I have noticed a significant trend that highlights the progression in experience and knowledge about CCUS. We have moved from discussing the technical barriers to addressing the more complex issues of policy and finance challenges. Those countries that are a driving force in CCUS development must serve as institutional knowledge centers and business development catalysts for those who are in the process of evaluating and deciding whether this technology is a suitable and feasible alternative based on their particular contexts.

Although CCUS is considered a transitional technology, it is also likely that we will use it for many generations. It all depends on the pathways society decides to follow. One critical sector that is determinant to achieve a sustainable future is energy. Energy systems are complex and strongly depend on their balance. Therefore, we need to continue having options regarding our energy usage and production that balance environmental impacts, allowing an economic stability, and contribute to social well-being. Therefore, it is essential to think in systems - ecosystems, climate, energy, and social systems - and recognize that they overlap and change through feedback.

If society organizes and comes together, soon, with a shared vision for the future of our energy and climate systems, we will likely meet the emissions reduction goals by 2050. This is an essential part of the sustainable future vision. Still, this probability differs depending on the scenario we choose, and the goal will continue to shift as we move forward in time. The question becomes; what happens when the 2022 goal is no longer enough? When does that happen?

To answer and continue to refine our answer over time, we need a balance between collection and access to data, models development, and refinement of the multiple systems in which we interact. I am optimistic that humans are very creative and somewhat self-focused. If we believe we can, we will reduce emissions at the defined scale. In the worst scenario, society will lose hope or be trapped in the perverse argument of multiple factions/sides about what is best, missing the opportunity for a positive transformation. Imaging our possible futures is a powerful tool to help and guide our actions toward a sustainable transformation.

These are some possible futures to think about:

Do nothing - A future based on the current situation moving slower than needed, challenges with infrastructure development, aspirational goals (Net Zero by 2050) instead of practical solutions, vilification of fuel sources instead of focusing on emission reduction, justice issues and inequality of burden, unwillingness to have hard conversations and make hard choices... the result is that things will stay relatively the same or continue to decline.

Do everything focusing in one direction - A future based on the anti-fossil fuel desires of progressive environmentalists where we stop using all fossil-based fuels immediately. Unwillingly we will create more inequity by shutting down possible energy streams, there is not going to be enough energy for all, blackouts will be frequent, unstable geo-political situation, too many changes, too fast for being able to adapt.

Create an integrative approach - A future based on an energy transition combining smart decisions, pursuing creative solutions, and integrating progressive and traditional values for social and environmental justice with safe economic choices. All of the above will serve to create a future with a hydrogen energy system, but does not exclude carbon-based fuels either.

We as a society need to align on share goals, create pragmatic and actionable solutions, and work together to move toward our sustainable future. It is important to have aspirations, but equally, if not more important, to have a defined path and be allowed to put solutions into action.

CONVERSANDO

CONVERSING

Pathways to more sustainable worlds: growth or degrowth?

Interview with **Carlos Muñoz Piña**

By **Paola Massyel García Meneses**

Carlos Muñoz studied Economics at the Instituto Tecnológico Autónomo de México (ITAM) in Mexico City, he has an MSc in Environmental Economics from the University College London in the United Kingdom, and a Ph.D. in Economics of Natural Resources at the University of California at Berkeley. He has been a professor-researcher at the ITAM, the Ibero-American University, and the Environmental University. He continues teaching courses and seminars at these and other institutions in Mexico, the United States, and the rest of Latin America.

The ways in which we as humans have lived for thousands of years have brought us to this moment. We share and compete for resources with millions of other living organisms, but it is not difficult to see that the human being and his social constructions have taken control and modified more and more aspects of the world, with consequences that range from the positive to the negative and to the uncertain.

A trajectory is the path that any object or subject follows when is moving from one point to another through time, from a stone to a civilization. For physics, the trajectory is the geometric place of the successive positions that the object or particle occupies in its movement. Both, an organism like a community and a system as connected as the Earth, have a trajectory. We hear more often now about the changes we need to make to change current trajectories so that we can lessen our future impacts on the world. To modify a trajectory, movement is necessary to change the current position and be able to reach another place. Changing the trajectory of an organism may not be as complicated as that of a community, but now imagine changing the trajectory of the world!

There are various world agendas, such as the Sustainable Development Goals, which point out, between consensus and common sense, where we want to go as a civilization and as a global community. But there is no single path to reach them; instead, there are millions of different routes. As we have seen in history and repeatedly, sadly, these global agendas are being postponed, with a respective name change: from "**Millennium Goals or MDGs**"¹ to "**Agenda 2030**", and now to the most recent "**Agenda 2050**". It is complex to

change trajectories on a scale as large as the global one, considering that we are subsystems that manage, think, feedback and change differently over time. However, there are philosophical currents that raise and propose interesting and disruptive ways to reach new horizons. One of them is the concept of degrowth, understood as the set of theories that criticize the paradigm of economic growth, which is based on ideas from a wide range of lines of thought such as political ecology, ecological economics and environmental justice, which indicate the ecological and social damage caused by the quest for infinite growth and Western development imperatives.

In particular, the theoretical, practical, and political current of degrowth emphasizes the need to reduce global consumption and production and advocates for a socially just and ecologically sustainable society in which the social and environmental well-being replace Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as an indicator of prosperity. To contrast perspectives, today we talked about degrowth with Dr. Carlos Muñoz Piña, an economist trained in sustainable growth theories.

Dr. Muñoz has dedicated himself to economic research aimed at solving environmental and natural resource challenges. In particular, he has worked in the analysis for the design, negotiation and evaluation of public policies. His emphasis has been on economic instruments for issues of environmental services, circular economy, energy efficiency, environmental taxes, energy markets, clean energy, and mitigation and adaptation to climate change.

¹ Eight human development goals set in the year 2000 by 189 member countries of the United Nations that they agreed to achieve by the year 2015.

Dr. Muñoz Piña has been a researcher and research coordinator at various government and academic centers, including the National Institute of Ecology and Climate Change (INECC) of the Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources (SEMARNAT), where he led the team that designed the federal Payment for Environmental Services program for forests, at the Mario Molina Center. In addition, he guided the team that designed the Carbon Tax proposal for Mexico and conducted basic research for the Clean Energy Market and the Emissions Trading System. In addition, he was chief economist for Forest Trends and has collaborated on the design of economic-environmental instruments with the World Bank and other multilateral development banks, with the USFS and the OECD, among others. From 2014 to 2018 he was Director of Revenue Policy at the Ministry of Finance and Public Credit, where he worked on fuel taxes and energy prices, before joining the Research, Data and Innovation area of the World Resources Institute global office.

Q: How would you understand the concept of degrowth?

A: Degrowth would imply that the amount of goods and services produced in an economy will be less in the following year than in the current year. The way economic growth is traditionally measured is with changes to the indicator we call **Gross Domestic Product (GDP)**: the estimated sum of value added in an economy, the estimated sum of what is paid for the goods and services produced in a period in a territory. Therefore, a society that **produces fewer goods and services** the following year than the current year would be **degrowing**. On the one hand, I would technically understand this as an **economic recession**, which normally generates a strong political reaction against it, because they are an indicator that a country is not doing the right thing so that investment in capital accumulates, in order for people to find more and better jobs and for more goods and services to be produced.

Q: Do you think degrowth strategies would work globally? For Mexico?

A: I'd like to talk first about places where I think growth strategies are working, at least partially. Countries that grow very fast reduce poverty very fast. For example, in China, more than 800 million people have come out of extreme poverty in the last 4 decades², nearly 20 million people per year! thanks to economic growth at average rates greater than 6% per year, on average, during those years. Growth rates of this level are not unique to China; we have observed them in other economies at different

scales, and for different periods of time. For example, in a contemporary way I can think of India since its market reform; Peru, in recent decades thanks to the boom in minerals and good management; in Mexico during a good part of the 1950s and 1960s, and, at the subnational level, in Mexico, the states of Aguascalientes and Querétaro since the 1990s. Of course, many environmental problems were associated with this growth, and it was possible to grow in a more clean, more sustainable way. There are ways to do it.

This correlation that we see between **economic growth** and **poverty alleviation** can be found at different scales, in different regions. Regions or economies that are growing at more than 5% per year, for example, begin to attract people from other places, migrant populations, which help to continue growth. Economic growth means that there are more goods and services

on average per person; if the distribution of income is not extremely inequitable, then most people will be better off. The definition of "being better", or having greater well-being, as it is also identified in economic theory, comes in this case from the fact that a higher income allows buying more goods and services to satisfy needs and interests.

Another important concept to bring to the discussion is the level of **extreme poverty**, where it is calculated what would be the income of a household that, when used with the common consumption pattern in a region, would prevent malnutrition of people in that household. And of course, with malnutrition a vicious circle is generated, since it prevents taking advantage of all the capacities of people to get out of poverty itself. Countries that have high percentages of their population in extreme poverty,

when their economy and employment grow, reduce the portion of people in that situation. However, we cannot rule out that there is unfair growth, where the incomes that are growing the most are those of the middle classes or higher income groups.

Given that the general pattern observed is that when countries grow, the number of people in poverty decreases, when I think about the concept of **degrowth**, my first reaction would be to apply it only to countries with high income levels and low percentages of people in poverty. It would only apply for its highest income groups.

² Zhang, Tongjin, Yuan Zhang, Guanghua Wan, and Haitao Wu. "Poverty reduction in China and India: a comparative study." *The Singapore Economic Review* 65, no. supp01 (2020): 95-115.

Taking as an example the consumption of the richest 20% of households in the richest countries of Europe, North America and Asia, and the richest 5% of households in developing countries, they have a footprint of consumption of goods and services so high that, from a moral point of view and in practical environmental terms, their consumption of more would not seem necessary. Why do they want another car, even bigger? New clothes every week? It is not difficult to see it as **superfluous consumption**, consumption that competes for resources that would be better left in place. In this sense, **degrowth** could work, but only for certain groups, for certain countries; In a certain way, I believe that it can be applied through taxes on income, wealth and overuse of natural resources, including the influence of decision frameworks on consumption, with other environmental policies, but it would not apply the idea of degrowth to the most vulnerable countries and portions of the population; It doesn't make sense.

This type of balance is what is behind the new currents of thought that are combining ideas of the sustainable development goals with policies to reduce inequality, for example, what is written about Beyond GDP (Fleurbaey, 2009³; Aitken, 2019⁴) and the Donut Economy (Raworth, 2017⁵). These, and others, in terms of objectives, ways of measuring progress, I see them well. Despite the interesting nature of the discussion, I believe that the most useful thing would be to discuss the specific instruments to achieve these objectives. There would be a better agreement on the actions to follow, even with currents that have no problem with economic growth. The most important discussion would be about what policies can bring us to this balance. And I am thinking both of those actions that are politically feasible in the short term and those that are more ambitious, but which, if they do not begin to ask forcefully at once, will not be achieved in time.

Perhaps my main problem with the theory of degrowth is with one of its roots, in particular with the one that comes from the 1970s, through the "Limits to Growth"⁶ current, since it starts from a vision of systems where there is no way for the economic system to react with effective responses to the scarcity of natural resources. For economic analysis, that reaction does exist and it comes in the form of prices. And of course, the economic literature has grown to identify market failures and government failures that prevent these signals from

being formed or expressed, and proposes policy instruments to do so with the necessary force to move towards energy savings and materials, investment in alternatives for it, innovation and its adoption.

Q: Are there any cases where some degrowth strategy is working?

A: I can talk about "local degrowth" strategies that are working. It would be local since it would only apply to a part of the economic activity, a sub-sector or a sub-region. This would be the first list of examples from Mexico but is also applicable to other economies:

- When a **protected natural area** is established, such as a national park or a Biosphere Reserve, and there is effective monitoring and surveillance, mineral or forestry extraction permits are canceled in its core area, and agricultural activities are stopped to allow restoration of natural ecosystems, then in that area we would **have a decrease** in economic activity. The National Commission for Natural Protected Areas (CONANP) in Mexico has been successful in **reducing** economic pressure in several of the core areas of Biosphere Reserves. This is a local decrease, but, to avoid a general drop in income among the households of people who own or live in the land where these ecosystems are located, the management plans allow activities, with sustainability criteria, in areas surrounding. There are also payments for environmental services and ecotourism, which generate income without further extraction of resources or changes in land use. It remains to do the math, area by area, with evidence and frequency, but I see it as an example where the idea of decrease can be applied with balance. Of course, we can take the perspective of environmental economics⁷, or ecological economics⁸, and estimate the value of ecosystem services, expressed with or without the market, and when added, we would surely find that these areas are generating even greater value for society. In the Parallel Accounts system carried out by INEGI, the adjusted GDP would be higher with conservation!

³ Fleurbaey, M. (2009). Beyond GDP: The quest for a measure of social welfare. *Journal of Economic literature*, 47(4).

⁴ Aitken, A. (2019). Measuring welfare beyond GDP. *National Institute Economic Review*, 249, R3-R16.

⁵ Raworth, K. (2017). *Doughnut economics: seven ways to think like a 21st-century economist*. Chelsea Green Publishing.

⁶ Meadows, D., & Randers, J. (2012). *The limits to growth: the 30-year update*. Routledge.

⁷ Mendelsohn, Robert, and Sheila Olmstead. "The economic valuation of environmental amenities and disamenities: methods and applications." *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 34, no. 1 (2009): 325-347.

⁸ Hein, Lars, Kris Van Koppen, Rudolf S. De Groot, and Ekko C. Van Ierland. "Spatial scales, stakeholders and the valuation of ecosystem services." *Ecological economics* 57, no. 2 (2006): 209-228.

- In **taxes on fossil fuels**, we have another example that I consider valuable. In Mexico, the carbon tax approved in Mexico by Congress in the IEPS bill for 2014 and continued until its current version, as well as other taxes, especially applied to gasoline and diesel, it raise the cost of all fuels fossils (except natural gas, but that's another story). Remember what gasoline cost in the early 2010s? What a huge difference from prices in the early 2020s. Back then it was heavily subsidized, and none of these taxes applied. In a research project whose results will soon be published in the journal *Economics of Energy & Environmental Policy*⁹, two colleagues and I found that the net effect of removing subsidies and putting a price on carbon via taxes was not only to reduce gasoline consumption and diesel compared to what would have been if the subsidies had been maintained (the counterfactual), but the **total consumption** of these fuels **was reduced**, even before the closures of the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. A lower emission of local and global pollutants with the same or greater economic activity! This effect on savings and efficiency was the product of millions of microdecisions, in the medium and long term, of companies and consumers. It happened over half a decade, since the change in the final price was gradual, and has been consolidated until today (except for the small subsidy that returned in 2022, but that is another story, which you can read in the article). We could see the connection with the **decrease** in the fact that, indeed, less of these two fuels were consumed. Lower consumption implies lower imports or lower production. In this sense, the decrease in fossil fuel activity in Mexico left us better off as a society, generated more taxes for public spending and better air

quality, helping to fulfill the global commitment. Is it a local effect? Yes, in geography and time, because as household income grows in Mexico there is economic pressure to consume more, and it could already be a valuable gain compared to the counterfactual, although not an absolute gain. We would need a higher level of taxes to increase climate ambition. With improvements in cleaner public and private transport alternatives – electric, for example – it is possible and desirable.

I would stop at these two examples, although there are several others that I would recommend reviewing, including the ideas of circular economy, agriculture with fewer agrochemicals, more compact cities, and sustainable fishing; each with its economic and regulatory instruments.

And we need more. I would call on your readers to design and promote, to research and communicate, new options for the ever-pending and growing environmental agenda. I would love to read these where there are new economic instruments (environmental, multi or transdisciplinary economy) and impact entrepreneurship, to gradually solve the problems of water pollution in Mexico, sulfur in fuels, the economy that is not yet circular, pollutants from short life for Mexico's commitments to the Paris Agreement, in the deep decarbonization necessary for 2050, and of course, defending ecosystems and their biodiversity from the continuous pressures of growth and infrastructure. All this by improving income and reducing the various dimensions of poverty in Mexico. It doesn't matter what paradigm they use to decipher the questions; with science and public policies based on evidence, we are going there.

⁹ Vol. 11, No. 2.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Imagining future scenarios is a tool to support and guide actions towards sustainability and allows us to address long-term challenges considering complexities and uncertainties of the world we inhabit.

The co-production of the following scenarios is a joint effort to explore ideas and analyzing different perspectives about managing carbon emissions and sustainability. We are seeking to motivate the imagination of our readers and encourage the development of strategies to create a more just and sustainable future for all.

THE THREE SCENARIOS

PLAUSIBLE

what can we build with what we know and have now?

PROBABLE

¿what can be achieved if specific conditions are met?

PREFERABLE

what is the best thing that could happen?

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SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

PLAUSIBLE SCENARIO

The knowledge and technology we have today are powerful tools that can help us redesign our future.

Marine and terrestrial ecosystems protection is a priority and can be achieved through regulatory improvements that promote reforestation campaigns, restoration of soils and bodies of water, as well as the creation of emission trading systems.

In large cities, green buildings are popularized, and public transport and cleaner vehicles (train, bicycles, hybrid cars) are promoted. In rural areas, monocultures and fertilizers predominate, but efforts are made to integrate more environmentally friendly models and practices.

The need for fossil fuels and heavy industry (cement, petrochemical, steel) continues. The energy systems consist of large-scale renewables as well as thermoelectric with carbon capture, use and storage coupled with enhanced oil recovery (CCUS). These technologies are also combined through models such as bioenergy or energy generation plants from waste, both with CO₂ capture and storage.

References

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SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

PROBABLE SCENARIO

The preservation and restoration of ecosystems is a cross-cutting issue achieved through better governance mechanisms. Regulations are stricter, and the need to transform the economy and markets increases. Technological innovation and sustainability play a fundamental role and guide a just transition where there is a reorientation of capacities and visions of the “extractive” industry to a “sustainable” one.

The concentration of the population is in "smart" cities with the electrification of transport, the use of hydrogen and biofuels, and the massification of green buildings and corridors to improve air quality. Alternatives for urban gardens are integrated for food supply.

Energy systems rely heavily on large-scale renewables. Technologies such as direct air capture (DAC) are necessary. And new industries such as mining for strategic minerals and rare earths elements are created in garbage and e-waste dumps. Circular economy models are promoted.

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SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

PREFERABLE SCENARIO

There are self-organized social structures based on degrowth and decentralization. Ruralization and economies of scale allow better management of resources and the emergence of new models of governance and regulation that give rights and protect humans and nature alike. Different sources of knowledge are integrated, such as ancestral and indigenous knowledge, in agriculture (agroecology and polycultures) and engineering (ecotechnologies).

Technology allows a balance between society and ecosystems. Some organisms evolve to assimilate microplastics and other contaminants present in water, soil and air.

Energy systems are based on small-scale renewable energy, electrification of transport and use of non-fossil fuels. New materials and circular models emerge that allow the transformation and processing of waste (including CO₂) into valuable products. All industries use technologies to control and reduce emissions and waste.

References

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PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

Movie: *Nausicaä of the Valley of the Wind*

This Hayao Miyazaki film, released in 1984, shows a world in which humans live isolated in small colonies surrounded by a toxic forest, a thousand years after a devastating world war. The protagonist is a brave princess who believes that the forest and the animals that inhabit it are not evil and that there is a way to coexist in harmony.

<https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0087544/>

Cómic: *Let's save the Earth with CAP! Beautiful Earth, Our Planet*

This first comic was created and released in 2015 in Japan as part of the communication materials and involvement with the society of the CCS project in that country. This edition presents the problem of global warming and what we can do to help the Earth from the hand of CAP, the central character of these comics. This project was supported and supervised by the Japanese Ministry of Economy, Trade and Finance in collaboration with Japan CCS Co., Ltd.

https://www.japanccs.com/wp/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/CCS_manga_En_web_1607293.pdf

Cómic: *Let's learn with CAP! Technology for the future of our planet*

This second comic came out in 2016. In it, CAP introduces Nozomi and Sho to the technical and practical aspects of CCS, as well as their contribution to addressing climate change issues and the development of the CCS demonstration project in Tomakomai, north of Japan.

https://www.japanccs.com/wp/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/CCS2_en_web_allpage1.pdf

Videogame: *Half Earth Socialism*

Do you like challenges? Half Earth Socialism is a video game based on the book Half Earth Socialism, by Drew Pendergrass and Troy Vettese. This game will test your creativity and knowledge to design a plan to save the future of the Earth and bring well-being to all, through strategic decisions based on restoring biodiversity and carbon sinks, a rapid energy transition, changes in diets and eating patterns, consumption and land use, as well as planning to manage resources in a more efficient and equitable way.

<https://play.half.earth/>

Movies: *Mad Max*

The first Mad Max film, released in 1979, is a work of science fiction by George Miller that presents a "future" world and the conflicts arising from an excessive dependence on oil. Three sequels were later produced: The Road Warrior, Beyond Thunderdome and Fury Road. All of them reflect the serious social and environmental problems of a post-apocalyptic world in which the scarcity of resources stands out.

Book: *Transforming the Future*

This book is part of the UNESCO Futures Literacy project. It presents information and evidence from projects from 30 Future Literacy laboratories and 14 case studies around the world that explore the needs and opportunities for innovation in decision-making systems to design and achieve sustainable, inclusive futures, social well-being and peace. Download the book at the following link:

<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000264644>

Essay: *Black to the Future*

In this text, Mark Dery coins and explores the term Afrofuturism, which corresponds to the intersection of African culture with elements of science fiction, technology, and the future. The text is organized in the form of interviews with important science fiction writers who, together, express the feelings and concerns of the African American community and the African diaspora in the context of the technological culture of the twentieth century, with an eye to the future. With its publication in 1994, the essay had a major effect on the creation of the Afrofuturist movement.

Documentary: *Ten Billion*

Stephen Emmott, Director of Computer Science at Microsoft Research, brought together a team of scientists to predict what challenges humanity would face in the future. The conclusions of the work indicate that at the end of this century the planet would have 10,000 million inhabitants. The documentary addresses the consequences that this "overpopulation" could have, given the finite resources of our planet.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BzA-9T-r2Vs>

Mexico City, Mexico, 2022